

Levels of Attainment in Higher Education: A Spatio-Temporal Analysis in India

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Abstract

Attaining higher knowledge is a capital for a variety of needs: employment opportunities, enhance productivity, and income, good health, a higher social and political contribution for making fair social and economic order, and improving individual's personal and enriching social capabilities. There is glaring inequality in Indian society based on caste, class, gender, and region across the Indian society. The paper is an attempt to present a spatial analysis based on levels of attainment in higher education across India. Analysis reveals that there is a large spatial variation in the attainment rate of higher education among different sections of the society across the Indian states/UTs. However, the female attainment rate is comparatively better at the postgraduate level of higher education which is a positive sign of women empowerment.

Keywords: *Educational Attainment, Gross Enrollment, Higher-Education, India, Spatial-Disparity.*

Introduction

Education is an important tool to increase the level of the social and economic status of the society. There is variation in social and economic conditions based on caste, class, gender, region, and religion across India. This paper mainly presents a discourse of spatial variation in the attainment of higher education by examining the patterns of attainment rate in higher education both at the cumulated and disaggregated by socio-economic groups as well as inter-state levels. The enrollment pattern in higher education shows high regional variations both concerning enrollment and availability of higher education across the Indian states (Sinha and Srivastava, 2008). The overall enrollment in higher education has enhanced from 1.73 lakhs in 1950-51 to 95.1 lakhs in 2002-03 (MHRD, 2003). The data of the Census of India 2001 and 2011 also shows an increase in the total GER in higher education from 13.50% in 2001 to 24.45% in

2011 (Census of India, 2011). Moreover, MHRD mentioned that a total of 15% of students were enrolled in higher education in 2009-10 (AISHE, 2016) which has grown 24% total enrollment in 2014-15 (MHRD, 2016). Therefore, this paper has tried to find out that what the actual achievement rate of higher education is after getting enrollment in higher education among the different sections of the society as well as at the state level. Thus, it is probable that this analysis has been done based on the educational attainment rate (EAR) in higher education that will highlight perceptions of the problems challenging attainment patterns in higher education in India.

The present research paper has been divided into three major sections. Firstly, it presents a brief discussion of enrollment in higher education along with figurative analysis of the trend pattern of enrollment in higher education for the whole country. Secondly, it describes the pattern of attainment in higher education in terms of attainment rate among the different social groups. The third section focuses on analyzing spatial patterns of attainment rate in higher education at different level i.e. aggregated, graduate and post-graduate level of education. Additionally, this section also analyzes the male-female spatial disparity among the states/UTs of India. Finally, in the concluding lines, it explains the status of the attainment rate at higher education levels in India.

Data Sources and Methodology

Present research paper is primarily based on secondary data extracted from Census of India 2011 for analyzing the enrollment and attainment pattern in higher education are: 1) Social-Cultural Table C-Series: Census of India, 2011; 2) C-8: Education Level by Age and Sex for all of Age 7 and above; and 3) C-10: Population Attending Educational Institutions by Age, Sex, and Type of Educational Institution. Moreover, MHRD and other government reports and publications, reports of national and international agencies have been used to supplement our analysis.

The gross enrollment ratio (GER) is the total amount of enrolled students at a particular level of education proportional to the related age group. We have a computed gross enrollment ratio in higher education by using the equation, $GER(\text{higher education}) = \frac{\text{All Enrolled in Post-Higher Secondary Classes}}{\text{Total Population in 18-24 age group}} \times 100$ (Sinha, 2008). Educational

attainment may be defined as the level of educational completion for the specific age group with a specific educational level in the age group (Sinha and Srivastava, 2008). Thus, Net Attainment Rate (NAR) in higher education is the level of educational completion for the age group of 20-24 years that is the percentage of persons with a higher education level in the same age group.

The spatial pattern of inequality in EAR of higher education has been analyzed by using Sopher's index (modified by Kundu) to capture the disparity between male and female. This index has been used to look into the disparity in EAR at the state level by using the Kundu's index formula (Kundu, 1980). All the states/UTs of the country have been classified into four categories of level of performance reference with the spatial pattern of educational attainment and disparity index i.e. low, medium, high and very high level. The Regional (inter-state) variation in the level of educational development has been measured with the help of simple Co-efficient Variation (C.V.) by using the formula, $CV = SD/mean * 100$.

Results

Educational attainment in higher education firstly and directly depends upon the accessibility to higher education that refers to get enrolled in the tertiary level of education i.e. post-secondary levels of education. The total enrollment in higher education has grown from 1.73 lakhs in 1950-51 to 95.1 lakhs in 2002-03 (MHRD, 2003). According to MHRD (2016), total enrollment in higher education was 8.1% for the whole country. However, it was recorded a large variation in terms of region, religion, caste, class, and gender at a different level across India.

Source: Educational Statistics at a Glance, MHRD, Department of School Education & Literacy, Government of India 2016.

The number of private higher educational intuitions has increased rapidly after the liberalization of the Indian economy along with with new public sector higher educational intuitions. An increasing number of colleges/institutions along with the implementation of the new government social welfare schemes to get higher education for deprived sections of Indian society has attracted a large section of the population for higher education. It has boosted the number of enrollment in higher education that was recorded at 8.1% in 2001-02. After that it is was constantly increasing with little fluctuation annually till (15%) 2009-10. The proportion of enrollment in higher education has recorded an accelerating rapid increase from 2010-11 onwards i.e. it was reached from 15% to 24.30% in 2015-16 (Figure-1). According to Data of Census of India 2001 and 2011, it also shows a tremendous increase in the total GER in higher education from 13.50% in 2001 to 24.45% in 2011 (Census of India, 2011).

Educational Attainment

Educational attainment in higher education has been discussed here in terms of percentage of the population those who have completed higher education. The analysis of educational attainment among the different social groups is based on the Census of India 2011.

All Category				
Age Group	15-19 year	20-24 year	25+ year	All Ages
Higher Secondary	11.8	18.1	7.2	7.5
Graduate & Above	-	11.8	9.1	6.5
Non-Scheduled				
Higher Secondary	13.3	19.8	8.1	8.4
Graduate & Above		13.7	10.7	7.8
Scheduled Castes				
Higher Secondary	8.5	14.3	4.7	5.2
Graduate & Above		7.1	4.4	3.2
Scheduled Tribes				
Higher Secondary	5.7	11.1	3.4	3.7
Graduate & Above		4.1	2.9	2.0

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

Table 1 shows that the educational attainment for the whole population of India is significantly low at the higher education level. It indicates that a total of 7.5% of the population of all age groups having a higher secondary level of education. It is 11.8% for the 15-19 year age group, 18.1% for 20-24 years of age group and 7.2% for more than 25 year age group having a secondary level of education. The proportions of the population having a higher secondary level of education are eligible to get enrolled in the post-higher secondary level of education. Generally, there is a decrease in the proportion of students' transition from higher secondary to post-higher secondary education. i.e. students have completed higher education transitioned from population eligible for higher education after enrolling in the post-higher secondary level of education. Overall, the net attainment rate in higher education for the whole of India has recorded 11.8% of the total. However, it varies when we consider it for different age groups. It is 9.1% for the age group of more than 25 years and 6.5% for all ages.

Furthermore, table 1 shows the distribution of the population by social groups having attained the higher secondary and graduate and above level of education by age. It indicates that only 7.1% of scheduled Castes in 20-24 years of age have attained graduation and above education. It records 4.4% for SC population aged 25 and above, and 3.2% for all ages. Similarly, only 4.1% of scheduled tribes in 20-24 years of age have accomplished graduation and above level of education. Moreover, it shows 2.9% for scheduled tribes population aged 25 and above, and 2.0% for all ages.

On the other hand, nearly 14% Non-Scheduled in 20-24 age and 11% aged 25 and above have completed the graduation and above degrees. In all ages above 7 years ago, 11% of the Non-Scheduled have accomplished graduation and above level of degrees, while it shows only 3.2% for scheduled castes and 2% for the Scheduled Tribes population. Thus, there are substantial gaps present in educational attainment at post-higher secondary level i.e. higher education level among the different social groups.

Spatial Pattern of Educational Attainment

The spatial pattern of educational attainment in higher education has been analyzed in terms of the net attainment rate (NAR) in higher education at the state level across India. Moreover, regional variations of male-female disparity have also been analyzed with the help of the choropleth map of disparity score (Sopher's Index) in the following section.

Net Attainment Rate at Graduate Level

Overall, net educational attainment in higher education (all levels of higher education) for India has recorded 11.82% of the total. However, there is a gap between male and female's net educational attainment rates of higher education. The proportion of male and female students' net attainment rate (NAR) in higher education at the country level shows 12.21% and 11.41% of the total respectively. The inter-state variation (CV) for total students' net attainment rate (NAR) in higher education has recorded 50.39% among the different states/UTs; while it is 48.29% for male students and 55.10% for female students (Table-2).

Variation	Person	Male	Female
NAR India	11.82	12.21	11.41
Mean	11.56	11.15	12.10
Standard Deviation	5.83	5.38	6.67
Coefficient of Variation	50.39	48.29	55.10

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

The spatial pattern of the net educational attainment rate (NAR) of higher education has been shown in Map-1. The state-wise pattern of NAR for total students shows that NCR of Delhi registers the highest NAR in higher education with 24.72% followed by Chandigarh, Puducherry, Kerala (20%) and Uttarakhand (20%). On the other hand state, Assam stands the lowest level with 4.64% preceded by Tripura (4.68%), Daman & Diu and Meghalaya. The spatial scenario shows that a total of 5 out of 35 states/UTs come under a very high level of NAR in higher education. Among the remaining states/UTs falling under high, medium and low levels of performance in NAR records 4, 8 and 18 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-1).

The state-wise pattern of male-female disparity (SI) indicates that the state of Bihar records the highest disparity score with 0.25 in NAR of higher education followed by Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, and West Bengal. On the contrary, Daman & Diu registers the lowest disparity score with -0.28 preceded by Lakshadweep, Goa, and Punjab. There are 18 states/UTs having negative disparity index and 3 having no male-female disparity. Remaining 14 out of 35

states/UTs are showing positive male-female disparity scores. The spatial picture of male-female disparity shows that 4 out of 35 states/UTs come under a very high level of disparity score in NAR of higher education. Remaining states/UTs show the high, medium and low level of disparity score in NAR of higher education records 15, 8 and 8 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-2). The states/UTs showing a negative disparity score indicate that female student having better performance in the completion of higher education in comparison to male students in the respective state/UTs. However, there is a spatial as well as gender disparity in the net attainment rate (NAR) of higher education across India.

Net Attainment Rate at Graduate Level

The net attainment rate in graduate other than a technical degree for India has registered 7.06% of the total. The proportion of male and female students' net attainment rate in graduate other than technical degree shows 7.28% and 6.83% of the total respectively that indicates the existence of a gap between male and female's net attainment rate. There is an inter-state variation (CV) in NAR in graduates other than a technical degree for the whole country shows 43.27% among the states/UTs; while it is 40.08% for male students and 49.85% for female students (Table-3).

Variation	Person	Male	Female
NAR India	7.06	7.28	6.83
Mean	7.03	6.70	7.43
Standard Deviation	3.04	2.68	3.71
Coefficient of Variation	43.27	40.08	49.85

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

The regional pattern of NAR in graduate other than technical degree suggests that NCR of Delhi registers highest NAR with 17% followed by Chandigarh, Uttarakhand, Kerala (12%) and Goa; while, on the contrary Daman & Diu stands lowest level with 3.43% preceded by Tripura, Assam, and Chhattisgarh (Map-3). The spatial pattern of NAR in graduate other than technical degree shows that only one out of 35 states/UTs i.e. NCR of Delhi registers a very high level of NAR. Among the remaining states/UTs having the high, medium and low levels in NAR in graduate other than technical degree have recorded 4, 10 and 20 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-3).

Regional pattern of the male-female disparity in NAR in graduate other than technical degree shows that the Bihar records highest disparity score with 0.25 in NAR of higher education followed by Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, and West Bengal. On the contrary, Daman & Diu registers the lowest disparity score with -0.28 preceded by Lakshadweep, Goa, and Punjab. There are 18 states/UTs having negative disparity index in NAR in graduate other than a

technical degree and 3 state/UTs have no male-female disparity score. Among the remaining 12 out of 35 states/UTs have registered positive male-female disparity scores. The spatial picture of the male-female disparity in NAR in graduate other than technical degree shows that 4 out of 35 states/UTs come under the very high level of disparity score in NAR of higher education. Remaining states/UTs show the high, medium and low level of male-female disparity score in NAR in graduate other than technical degree records 15, 8 and 8 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-3). The states/UTs showing a negative disparity score indicate that female student having better performance in the completion of graduate other than a technical degree in comparison to male students in the respective state/UTs. From the above discussion, it is clear that there is a spatial as well as gender disparity in the net attainment rate (NAR) of graduates other than technical degrees across India.

Net Attainment Rate at Post-Graduate Level

The net attainment rate in completion of post-graduate other than a technical degree for India records 1.85% of the total. The proportion of male and female students' net attainment rate in post-graduate other than technical degree has recorded 1.59% and 2.13% of the total respectively. Overall, inter-state variation (CV) in NAR in post-graduate other than a technical degree for India shows 64.73% among the states/UTs; while it is 61.56% for male students and 70.39% for female students (Table-4). Thus, female students across the states/UTs suffer from higher variation in the completion of a post-graduate level of education in comparison to male students.

Table-4			
Inter-State Variation (C.V.) in Net Attainment Rate of Post-Graduate other than Technical Degree, 2011			
Variation	Person	Male	Female
NAR India	1.85	1.59	2.13
Mean	1.72	1.37	2.11
Standard Deviation	1.11	0.84	1.49
Coefficient of Variation	64.73	61.56	70.39

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

Source: Computed from C-Series Table, Census of India, 2011

The state-wise pattern of NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree suggests that Uttarakhand records highest NAR with 4.62% followed by Chandigarh, Uttarakhand, NCT of Delhi and Haryana; while, on the contrary Assam stands lowest level with 0.02% preceded by Bihar, Tripura, Meghalaya, and Mizoram (Map-5).

Generally, the regional scenario of NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree shows that 3 out of 35 states/UTs records a very high level of NAR. Among the remaining states/UTs having the high, medium and low levels in NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree have recorded 3, 11 and 18 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-5).

The state-wise pattern of the male-female disparity in NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree shows that the Andhra Pradesh registers the highest disparity score with 0.14 followed by Bihar, Tripura, Jammu & Kashmir, and Odhisa. On the other hand, Daman & Diu registers the lowest disparity score with -0.46 preceded by Punjab, Goa, Chandigarh, and Lakshadweep.

Overall, only 2 out of 35 states/UTs having positive male-female disparity scores in NAR in post-graduate other than a technical degree and remaining 33 state/UTs have recorded negative male-female disparity. The spatial picture of the male-female disparity in NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree shows that only 2 out of 35 states/UTs come under the very high level of male-female disparity. Remaining states/UTs show the high, medium and low level of male-female disparity score in NAR in post-graduate other than technical degree registers 13, 15 and 5 out of 35 states/UTs respectively (Map-6). The states/UTs showing a negative disparity score indicate that female student having better performance in NAR of post-graduate other than a technical degree in comparison to male students in the respective state/UTs.

Here two important facts have been cleared that 1) higher proportion female is attaining a post-graduate degree in comparison to males almost in all states/UTs with few exceptions. However, females are lagging to males in NAR of higher education levels across India. Thus, it is clear that there is a spatial, as well as gender disparity, that exists in the net attainment rate (NAR) of higher education across India.

Discussion

India is a vast country having several kinds of diversities across the region. It has diversified geographical features like physiography, climatic conditions, means of livelihood, and different social origin of people like ethnicity, linguistic, religion, and region. The highly diversified nature of India defines the socio-economic conditions of different social groups. Spatial, as well as temporal variation in educational attainment, is determined by several socio-economic factors that play an important role in access and accomplishing the particular level of education. As our analysis focuses three social groups indicate that the GER and EAR of 'Non-Scheduled' are invariably higher than the GER of Scheduled population in almost all the states/UTs. However, all the social groups have not experienced much change in post higher secondary level of education in the same direction (Dubey, 2008).

For women, the dimensions of caste, class, region, etc. create accumulative disadvantages and bears several burdens of inequality (Chanana, 1993). The disability imposed upon women in traditional society confinement in the domestic domain (Béteille, 2003). Gender discrimination in enrollment in higher education is motivated by the traditional attitudes towards gender roles

and accountabilities. Therefore, women have lower enrollment rates than males irrespective of their socio-economic status (Dubey, 2008). Socio-economic factors attribute low access to higher education for women are lack of economic resources; the choice between dowries and educational expense, and being irrelevant for production, etc. in the family (Chanana, 2007). The status of women in higher education is a matter of interest, if not of concern, all over the world (Powar, 1999).

Moreover, educational achievement based on academic performance resulted from being born in advantaged social groups. Most of the male can access the education those belongs to an upper-class family of an urban area (Clancy, et al. 2007). Another important factor determines the educational attainment is the level of education of the family. The family members having a higher level of education make their children efficient in educational activities and serve as a form of 'surrogate' to achieve education (Foster and Rosenzweig, 1996).

The socio-economic status of parents highly influences their children's educational performance at a different level. The parents' education, occupation, family income, and completion of school education are significantly and positively correlated with access and accomplishing a higher level of education (Tomul and Polat, 2013). Parents' employment has positively correlated to their children's educational attainment highly influenced by the parents' employment pattern (Cusworth, 2016). Household wealth promotes students to access higher levels of academic achievement (Jez, 2008). Household wealth created by an economic condition that is the most significant factor to determine the higher education Students from households with scarce sources of income is largely unable to afford higher education because higher education is expensive. Therefore, household wealth has a significant effect on enrolling to achieve higher education (Filmer and Pritchett, 1999a).

The educational level of the head of the family affects the access to the achievement of higher education of the family members. First-generation students appear to be at disadvantages that perpetuate the lower educational attainment generally leads to slower economic conditions again lead to a low level of education. Thus, socio-economic factors highly influence the achievement of higher education as an individual as well as the whole society.

As it has cleared from the above discussion that socio-economic factors influence the accessibility and attainment of higher education and, these factors promote social as well as spatial disparity or variation in accomplishing higher education. Our analysis indicates that the level of male-female disparities in attainment narrows down in some states, expands in others and remains constant in a few states. In most of the states, however, women appear to have improved their position to a higher extent compared to male students, especially at the post-graduate level of education across the country. The disparities in post-higher secondary enrollment among the deprived social groups are higher in many states. Therefore, social and economic status plays a key role to determine the achievement in higher education.

Conclusion

Higher Education in India is hierarchal having different layers and different duration of times and is not evenly distributed across the Indian states/UTs. Numerous socio-economic factors still prevail in the country that affects the accessibility and attainability of higher education at a different level among the different social groups across India. Therefore, higher education suffers from glitches of spatial as well as temporal variation in enrollment and attainment among the different and social groups across the country. There is great inequality in the attainment of higher education among the different social groups across the states/UTs of India.

The analysis reveals that the educated population at higher education in different social groups differs and shows low as a whole. However, generally, the non-scheduled population has advantages of their social and economic background, so they are sufficiently capable to attain higher education with a good performance level. Nonetheless, the scheduled groups are substantially very low in terms of educational attainment in comparison to the Non-Scheduled population. It indicates that education has usually endured the Non-Scheduled population, especially at higher education levels. Though the female has performed well at the post-graduate level of education they are always lagging behind to male in case of overall higher education, graduate-level across India. In other words, the educational opportunities for the scheduled and female population have not been available for them despite several efforts initiated by the Government of India since Independent.

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